

GBC Working Group on Sustainability

Consultation Paper

IMPORTANT NOTICE

This consultation paper was prepared by the GBC Secretariat based on the discussions and inputs of a Working Group composed of experts drawn from GBC member and observer organisations. This paper does not present recommendations or policy proposals: rather, it presents a series of ideas for discussion and feedback by GBC's stakeholders and communities. These ideas reflect the key themes that emerged from the Working Group's discussions, but will not necessarily always fully reflect the views of individual Working Group members. None of the ideas, viewpoints or any other content in this paper should be taken to represent the policy or positions of the organisations to which Working Group members are affiliated.

Executive Summary

Biodata resources play a critical role in enabling research across biology, the life sciences and biomedicine, supporting researchers all over the world in storing, curating, preserving data and enabling these data to be accessed and reused to advance research and its application for societal benefit. However, despite their fundamental importance to the global research enterprise, the long-term sustainability of many biodata resources is far from secure: many are reliant on short-term competitive funding sources, sometimes from a single or very limited number of funders. If biodata resources are to be able to remain open to the world's researchers to access and use in a way that maximises the full global benefit from the world's research data, it is vital that more secure and sustainable approaches for their long-term funding are sought.

The Global Biodata Coalition (GBC) is a coalition of research funders that aims to stabilise and ensure sustainable funding for global biodata infrastructure. The GBC Board Working Group on Sustainability brings together representatives from GBC Member and Observer organisations to consider ways that funders could cooperate to support the global biodata resource infrastructure in a more sustainable manner. It has two key objectives:

- **To identify and share best practice for individual funders** — the Group explored challenges faced by individual funders that support biodata resources, and opportunities for funders to share good practice and assist each other in developing longer-term, more strategic and sustainable approaches for supporting the biodata resources that they fund.
- **To explore ways funders could cooperate internationally to sustain the global biodata resource infrastructure** — the Group developed a series of premises, principles and models for enhanced cross-funder partnerships to more equitably and reliably fund biodata resources critical to the global life science and biomedical research communities and explored ways in which funders could cooperate to develop and sustain the biodata infrastructure as a whole.

Based on its discussions, the Working Group identified a series of options for enhanced cross-funder cooperation, which are set out in this consultation paper and summarised below. This paper was discussed by the GBC's Board of Funders in March 2023, and the options were further developed and refined by the Working Group based on the Board's feedback.

These options are intended as a starting point for further discussion with GBC's stakeholders and communities - including research funders, biodata resource managers and the wider life sciences research community. We invite comments, inputs and ideas on this consultation paper from all those with an interest in developing and sustaining the global biodata infrastructure. GBC will use the outcomes of this consultation to develop a White Paper setting out a policy proposal and planned activities through which GBC and its member organisations will work together to support the long-term funding and sustainability of biodata resources.

Proposed Options

1. Options for individual Funders in funding and sustaining biodata resources

- a. **Encourage coordinated approaches for biodata infrastructure at national and regional levels:** implementation of funder mandates are facilitated by consolidation of national approaches and costs can be substantially reduced by avoiding duplications.
- b. **Develop and adopt strategic approaches to supporting biodata resources,** to include:
 - i. establishing clear policies and priorities for supporting biodata resources, consistent with funder mandates;
 - ii. seeking national and regional partners, especially when the funder's own mandate for infrastructure support is limited, and where other organisations have important national or regional responsibilities;
 - iii. tracking the usage of resources by their funded researchers and the community more broadly and factoring this into strategic planning.
- c. **Aim to reduce barriers to international collaboration wherever feasible:** GBC could assist by gathering and cataloguing experiences and refining emerging common principles.
- d. **Provide guidance and resources to assist biodata resources to develop sustainability plans:** this could again be facilitated by GBC and informed by work to document existing models that have been employed by Global Core Biodata Resources (GCBRs) — see below.

2. Principles and models for cross-funder cooperation to support biodata resources of global importance

- a. **Establish the broad principles set out in the Consultation Paper as a foundation** to develop shared approaches for the support of crucial biodata resources of international importance. These principles are:
 - i. Those who fund life science research share responsibility for ensuring that data resources are sustained.
 - ii. Life science research funders of all types should contribute to biodata resource sustainability.
 - iii. All life science research funders should contribute through means that are appropriate to their cases.
 - iv. Sustainability will be required both for existing resources and for new resources that are established in response to new data types and technologies.
 - v. Models of funding must not require payment at the point of use of biodata resources (submission, retrieval, etc.).
 - vi. Models for sustainability must cater for cases where funds cannot move across national borders.
 - vii. Biodata resources must develop governance structures that support the interests of funding organisations and the institutions that host biodata resources.
 - viii. Sustainability across the biodata resource ecosystem depends upon the openness of data they hold
 - ix. All biodata resources should have a clear strategy for sustainability, including appropriate succession plans.

- b. Document current funding and sustainability plans for GBC Global Core Biodata Resources:** identify models that have worked well and use these to refine and add to the initial models presented in this Consultation Paper. This work will be conducted in partnership with the GCBR Forum — which brings together senior managers of the Global Core Biodata Resources — and with partner funders to ensure that the models identified are viable and meet the needs of funders and resources.
- c. Prototype and test potential models to enhance sustainability in partnership with GCBR resources and GBC funders:** develop pilots of models supported by resources and funders to test their viability and success in enhancing sustainability.

3. Options for cross-funder cooperation to develop and sustain the global biodata infrastructure

- a. Secure enhanced and sustained funder investment in biodata research infrastructure** — including sustained long-term commitments from funders who already support biodata resources and encouraging funders who don't currently fund biodata resources to provide support in line with their remits. This might include:
 - i. developing a campaign to capture enthusiasm and support for sustainable biodata infrastructure.
 - ii. working collectively to build the evidence base on the return from investment from providing sustained funding to biodata resources.
- b. Coordinate approaches to ensure the stability and sustainability of the global biodata infrastructure** — GBC could play a key role in convening cross-funder efforts aimed at:
 - i. establishing good practice principles for funders on sustaining biodata resources throughout the resource lifecycle, including provisions for sunseting resources
 - ii. ensuring the biodata infrastructure develops to meet the evolving needs of research and user communities — tracking and responding to emerging trends and gaps in terms of domain coverage
 - iii. working with biodata resources to develop standards and good practices to ensure resources provide high quality, consistent, stable and responsive services for user communities.

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1. Introduction

1.1 The challenge

1. Researchers across the biological sciences, life sciences and biomedicine depend upon biodata resources to store, preserve, curate and provide access to research data. These biodata resources include deposition databases, which store research data, and knowledge bases which curate these data and enable its widespread use in research (see Anderson et al. 2017).
2. Biodata resources are accessed and used by hundreds of thousands of researchers all over the world. They play a critical role in advancing discovery and its application for societal benefit, and provide immense value to the communities they serve and society more broadly. For example, an independent evaluation published in 2021 to assess the value and impact of data resources provided by EMBL-EBI estimated that these resources had directly underpinned research impacts valued at £1.3 billion annually that could not otherwise have been realised (see Beagrie and Houghton 2021). The study, which updated an earlier 2015 report, also estimated that the benefit in terms of efficiency gains to users and their funders was worth between £2.6 billion and £11 billion per annum worldwide. Based on an estimated annual expenditure of £110 million, the study indicated these biodata resources provide a substantial return on investment.
3. Despite the value and critical importance of biodata resources in research, their long-term funding is often not secure (see Bourne et al. 2015). Many depend on short term grant funding, sometimes from a limited number of funders — making it difficult to plan with certainty for the long-term and provide their staff with job security. While several funders have made long-term commitments to support resources, resources may be in a perilous position should budgets fall or the strategic priorities of the funders on whom they depend for ongoing support change.
4. These challenges for resources are compounded by the continuing rise in data volumes and complexity and continuing growth of data-intensive science, including AI and machine-learning approaches. Meanwhile, the growth of the open science movement, with the development of new community standards, such as the FAIR and TRUST principles (see Wilkinson et al. 2016, Lin et al. 2020); the emergence of accreditation systems, such as Core Trust Seal (see L'Hours et al. 2019)); and increasingly stringent open data policy requirements from funders, publishers and research institutions are placing additional funding pressures on resources. The central role of biodata resources in driving the uptake of community standards and in ensuring the effective delivery of funder and publisher mandates provides a further imperative to ensure they are funded and sustained for the long-term.
5. To be sustainable, biodata resources individually and the infrastructure as a whole, needs to be maintained and developed over the long-term to meet the needs of user communities. Sustainability has many aspects: it requires effective governance, ongoing maintenance of technical and service standards and the ability to respond and adapt to rapid-evolving scientific and technical developments. Provision of adequate and stable long-term funding support is critical to ensuring sustainability and ensuring these other needs can be met, but it is in itself just one element of sustainability.
6. The need for resources to develop approaches to sustainability has long been recognised. Several reports from international and national working groups over recent years have

explored this issue — including groups convened by the OECD and US National Academies (see OECD 2017 and National Academies 2020). In Europe, the ELIXIR infrastructure has successfully brought together Europe’s biodata resources and encouraged a coordinated approach to manage and sustain the European biodata infrastructure — including through identifying ELIXIR core data resources (see Drysdale et al. 2020). But few concrete solutions to the challenges of long-term funding and sustainability have emerged, and funders and resources are still grappling with this challenge.

7. Furthermore, at present, funding contributions for resources do not reflect their global usage. For many globally relevant biodata resources, a small cohort of funders (and sometimes only a single funder) is providing ongoing support for all users worldwide. Many countries and funders whose researchers use biodata resources are currently not contributing funding to those resources. Broadening the pool of funders contributing to biodata resources will aid the development and sustainability of the infrastructure.
8. The current lack of coordination internationally may also be leading to some unnecessary duplication and inefficiencies. While some level of redundancy and competition is valuable to encourage innovation and provide stability, a more joined up and coordinated approach could bring benefits for funders, biodata resources and the broader research community.
9. The current lack of stable long-term funding may ultimately result in more biodata resources considering models involving access fees or other access constraints for some types of users or services. Whilst such models may be appropriate for some resources in some circumstances, there is a particular risk they will particularly disadvantage researchers in less well resourced settings. Maintaining open and unrestricted access to research data is key to ensuring global equity and maximising global benefit, and creates a key need for the world’s funders to work together to address this challenge.

1.2 The opportunity: a role for the Global Biodata Coalition

10. The Global Biodata Coalition (GBC) is a forum for research funders to better coordinate and share approaches for the efficient management and growth of biodata resources worldwide. The GBC aims to stabilise and ensure sustainable financial support for the global biodata infrastructure.
11. As a key part of its work, the GBC will identify and maintain a list of Global Core Biodata Resources (GCBRs) that are crucial for sustaining the broader biodata infrastructure. The GBC concluded the first GCBR selection process in December 2022, publishing an initial list of 37 resources (see Global Biodata Coalition 2022). In early 2023, it convened the GCBR Forum to bring together senior leaders from these resources to discuss issues relating to sustainability and other opportunities to work together to address common challenges. GBC is running a second round of selection for GCBRs in 2023 to give further resources a rapid opportunity to apply and ensure a more representative and inclusive GCBR list.
12. While GCBRs will be a key initial focus for the GBC’s work to develop and implement approaches to advance sustainability, there is a vital need to characterise and maintain an overview of the entire global infrastructure of biodata resources. In 2023, the GBC published a global inventory of biodata resources, providing a fuller picture of the global landscape of biodata resources than has been available previously (see Imker et al 2023). Using a machine learning-enabled natural language processing approach to mine the literature, the work

identified a corpus of 3,112 unique resources based on articles published between 2011 and 2021.

13. Sustainability is at the very heart of GBC’s mission and GBC has been established with a specific mandate to bring funders and other stakeholders together to address this challenge. It is the first dedicated organisation established by funders specifically to support cross-funder discussions and cooperation to place global resources on a more sustainable footing. It also now has a cohort of GCBRs with which to work to explore and test models for enhancing sustainability, and to ensure the models developed meet the needs of both funders and biodata resources.

1.3 The GBC Board Working Group on Sustainability

14. In early 2022, the GBC’s Board of Funders established two cross-funder Working Groups: one to explore the topic of Sustainability and the second to examine Open Data Strategies. Both Working Groups bring together senior representatives from GBC Member and Observer organisations and they are chaired by the Chair of the GBC Board. Each group was tasked with developing a Consultation Paper to explore the challenges and to set out ways forward for consideration by the GBC Board and consultation with the GBC’s wider stakeholder community.
15. The Working Group on Sustainability (referred to as “The Working Group” in this paper) included representatives from several GBC partner funders and resource providers, namely: EMBL-EBI, Genome Canada, the Indian National Centre for Disease Informatics and Research, Inserm, the Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics (on behalf of SERI), UKRI, the US National Science Foundation, the US National Institutes of Health, and Wellcome. The full membership of the Working Group is listed at **Annex A**.
16. The Working Group on Sustainability was tasked with identifying ways that funders could cooperate to fund data resources in a more sustainable manner. Based on its initial discussions the Group agreed to focus its Consultation Paper on two key objectives:
 - **To identify and share best practice for individual funders** — the Group explored challenges faced by individual funders that support biodata resources, and opportunities for funders to share experience and good practice in developing longer-term, more strategic and sustainable approaches for supporting the biodata resources that they fund.
 - **To explore ways funders could cooperate internationally to sustain the global biodata resource infrastructure** — the Group developed a series of premises, principles and models for enhanced cross-funder partnerships to more equitably and reliably fund biodata resources critical to the global life science and biomedical research communities and explored ways in which funders could cooperate to develop and sustain the biodata infrastructure as a whole.
17. This Consultation Paper was developed by the GBC Board Working Group on Sustainability with the support of the GBC Secretariat. The Working Group met four times to discuss the issues and formulate the ideas presented here for wider discussion and consultation. To help inform the discussions, the Secretariat undertook a web-based survey to collect information on existing policies, guidance and approaches from the organisations represented on the Working Group.

18. The Consultation Paper was discussed by the GBC Board of Funders at its in-person meeting in March 2023. It was then developed further by the Working Group based on the Board's feedback and inputs. GBC is keen to receive comments and feedback on the Paper from its key partners and stakeholders - including funding bodies (including those already engaged in GBC and those who are not), biodata resources (including the GCBR Forum) and the broader open data and research communities, including resource users and publishers.
19. Based on the feedback received, the GBC Secretariat will develop a White Paper setting out plans to enhance sharing of good practice for individual funders and explore collaborative approaches amongst funders to advance biodata resource sustainability for approval by the GBC Board.

1.4 Scope

20. The Working Group agreed the following broad parameters for the scope of this Consultation Paper:
 - **It presents a funder perspective on the challenges around sustainability** — the Working Group representatives discussed the challenges around sustainability from a funder perspective. Whilst there was representation from senior biodata resource managers on the Working Group, it is recognised that broader consultation with resources (as well as with a broader range of funders) will be required to ensure that any sustainability models ultimately developed meet their needs.
 - **The term “funder” is broadly defined** — whilst the membership of the GBC is currently made up of public funding agencies and not-for-profit research foundations, the term “funder” should be seen to apply to all organisations that fund life sciences and biomedical research, including commercial entities.
 - **The paper addresses sustainability in a broad sense** - as noted above, whilst provision of adequate and secure long-term funding is critical for sustainability, it is just one of a number of elements needed to ensure sustainability - which also include strong governance, maintenance of service and standards and the ability to track and adapt to evolving needs of users and new technologies. While much of this paper focuses on models for sustainable funding, the GBC takes a holistic view of sustainability and is committed to working with funders and resources to characterise and address all aspects to ensure the infrastructure is sustained for the benefit of research globally.
 - **The initial focus is on resources providing unrestricted access to data** — this Consultation Paper focuses initially on resources that provide open and unrestricted access to data. The Working Group emphasised the critical importance of extending discussions on sustainability to include resources that, while supporting open science, provide managed access to data in order to safeguard the privacy and confidentiality of human research participants, protect biodiversity or address biosecurity concerns. The GBC will seek to engage other key stakeholders, such as the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health, in considering issues for managed access resources.
 - **The initial focus is on ‘core resources’**— it has been agreed that efforts to enhance funder cooperation to support biodata resources are initially focused on Global Core Biodata Resources. However, the Working Group emphasised that many resources that do not fulfil the criteria to be designated a GCBR are still hugely important to specific research fields or communities and may likewise be critical priorities to fund and sustain. Since these such resources typically draw data from, or connect data with, the content of GCBRs, they are expected to achieve greater sustainability as the GCBRs themselves grow in sustainability.

However, it is expected that additional efforts will be warranted to secure the long-term health of these resources.

2. Funding Biodata Resources: Identifying and Sharing Best Practice for Individual Funders

2.1 Summary of issues considered by the Working Group

21. The funders represented on the GBC Working Group on Sustainability have a broad range of experiences in supporting biodata resources and considering challenges relating to their long-term funding and sustainability. Over the course of the Working Group's discussions, several areas were identified where there was scope for funders to share experiences and lessons learnt, and potentially work together to identify good practices to assist funders in developing their own strategies and approaches.
22. One key issue that emerged was that the ability of funders to support biodata resources, and the nature of the funding they were able to provide, was often limited by their mission and remit. For some public funders, the extent to which they are mandated to support databases and related infrastructures may be limited by the legislation under which they were created. In addition, other bodies at a national level may have specific responsibilities for prioritising and providing funding for major research infrastructures. For some charitable foundations, the extent to which funding research infrastructures directly falls within their charitable objectives might be open to varying interpretations.
23. Working Group members noted that much funding to support biodata resources still currently flows through investigator-led responsive funding mechanisms. This creates several challenges:
 - Activities to support resources often need to be formulated as research projects, or otherwise shoehorned into research grants. If successful, the resulting support may not be ideally suited to the long-term needs of the supported resource, and will necessarily be time-limited.
 - By their nature, requests to develop or sustain resources may not be judged as cutting-edge and innovative when competing against hypothesis-driven research. Reviewers may rank these proposals less favourably against these criteria, or in some cases be minded to recommend cutting such support from grants if budgets are limited.
 - Funding in this manner does not readily allow a strategic approach to be taken by funders in terms of which resources to prioritise for support, and may lead to some unnecessary duplication. There is a particular risk that it leads to fragmentation and silos if projects proposing to establish new project-specific resources are funded in isolation.
 - Short-term funding also makes it difficult for resources to formulate long-term strategy, since it is time-limited and securing future funding may require them to adopt changes to meet the requirements of new funding calls.
 - Funding Committees and other peer review processes may not have representation from those with expertise to assess the importance and need for a particular resource, or whether the support requested is appropriate for the resource to meet the needs of users.
24. There is a clear recognition amongst Working Group members and funders more broadly that funding data resources necessarily requires a more strategic approach. In this light, several of the funding organisations represented on the Working Group have developed targeted mechanisms to support biodata resources and related infrastructures. These have included long-term commitments to strategically important resources, capital investments in national or

regional-level data centres and bioinformatics institutes, and dedicated funding calls for research infrastructures and tools (including biodata resources).

25. Whilst dedicated funding streams have offered benefits in terms of providing earmarked funds for resources and allowing applications to be assessed via a common route by reviewers with specific expertise in resource provision, they have also raised challenges. In particular, Working Group members noted that:
- Budgets for these funds are typically limited, and demand from biodata resources and other infrastructures is often very high. Sometimes, award values are capped and resources may not be able to secure the funds they need to fully meet community needs.
 - In light of these pressures on funding, it can be problematic to comparatively assess applications from well-established resources (with demonstrated ongoing usage) for ongoing development with applications from newly-established resources in areas of unmet need, which may lack this track record and established usage.
 - On a related point, there was a feeling that established resources may feel under pressure to demonstrate that they are innovating and actively pursuing new developments in order to be competitive — this may expand the costs and may not always fully align with the needs of users who may not need new functionality but for whom continuity of existing services is essential.
 - It can be problematic to consider in isolation applications from resources based in one country that are component parts of larger transnational collaborations given that there may be dependencies on other parts of the consortium.
 - There are cases where funding organisations have partnered successfully with other funders at both a national and international level to coordinate funding or to co-fund resources, but co-funding is quite rare and often carries a significant overhead.
 - As with investigator-led awards, the grants provided through these schemes are typically time-limited (up to five years) with renewal sometimes far from certain given the high demand, so don't necessarily provide a route for long-term sustainable funding.
26. Funders have recognised the need to adopt a more strategic approach to sustaining funding for biodata resources, but most have yet to formulate a clear position. Members of the Working Group noted the importance of working with resources to establish dedicated sustainability plans. They also discussed the need to tailor support to the resource lifecycle — from establishment and scaling up of new resources through to sustained funding for established resources, with provisions for sunseting once a resource was no longer required. This is an approach some funders already use to frame their funding. For example, the Research Resources Cluster within the Division of Biological Infrastructure at the US National Science Foundation offers separate funding streams for resources and tools at different levels of maturity — entitled 'innovation' (for innovative research to develop methods and tools), 'capacity' (for activities to scale-up resources and tools) and 'sustaining' (to provide continued support for established resources and tools).
27. Working Group members noted the need to adopt clear criteria for strategic decisions over which resources to prioritise for long-term funding, and associated decisions over the establishment of resources to meet unmet needs. Ideally, such decisions should be underpinned by robust data on the current and future requirements of the research community supported by the funder, and other key user communities integral to the funder's mission. At present, funders do not have access to robust and consistent data on demand and usage and it is an area where there may be scope for resources to work with funders to identify key data needs.

28. There is also a need for funders and resources to consider and respond to emerging challenges and trends in their ongoing support of resources—such as the costs and opportunities of cloud-based provision and the continuing development of artificial intelligence and machine learning approaches — which may place new demands on resources (see Section 3 below).
29. There is limited guidance from funders to resources to help them plan for long-term sustainability, in terms of models they could consider and experience on which they can draw. Partially as a result of the lack of clarity within funders around how to support resources sustainably, resources are often asked to develop approaches to become sustainable and find other sources of funding or revenue without receiving any assistance or support in terms of what models might be viable or acceptable to the funder.

2.2 Options proposed

30. The initial exchanges of information relating to previous and ongoing activities of the organisations represented on the Working Group in relation to funding biodata resources were hugely valuable. There is a large amount of existing experience on which funders can draw in considering their own strategies for funding biodata resources, as well as some significant remaining challenges where ongoing dialogue and cross-funder coordination are needed. Working Group members agreed strongly that the GBC could play a vital role in providing a forum for these discussions and providing resources for individual funders.
31. Based on its discussions, the Working Group identified some further options for individual funders to consider in funding biodata resources. These are listed in **Box 1** below.

Box 1 — Options for Individual Funders in funding and sustaining biodata resources

It is proposed that individual research funders consider the following options:

- a. **Encourage coordinated approaches for biodata infrastructure at national and regional levels:** implementation of funder mandates are facilitated by consolidation of national approaches and costs can be substantially reduced by avoiding duplications.
- b. **Develop and adopt strategic approaches to supporting biodata resources,** to include:
 - i. establishing clear policies and priorities for supporting biodata resources, consistent with funder mandates;
 - ii. seeking national and regional partners, especially when the funder’s own mandates for infrastructure support are limited, and where other organisations have important national or regional responsibilities; and
 - iii. tracking the usage of resources by their funded researchers and the community more broadly and factor this into strategic planning.
- c. **Aim to reduce barriers to international collaboration wherever feasible:** GBC could assist by gathering and cataloguing experiences and refining emerging common principles.
- d. **Provide guidance and resources to assist biodata resources to develop sustainability plans:** this could again be facilitated by GBC and informed by existing models employed by the Global Core Biodata Resources (see Section 3 below)

3. Principles and Models for Cross-Funder Cooperation to support biodata resources

3.1 Issues considered by the Working Group

32. In addition to considering issues at the level of individual funders, the second key objective for The Working Group was to explore ways in which funders could cooperate internationally to support the global biodata infrastructure in a fair, equitable and sustainable manner. In its discussions, the Group distinguished two 'levels' of sustainability:
- **Sustainability at the level of biodata resources** - what models could funders employ to ensure biodata resources of global importance are funded in a more stable, robust and sustainable manner?
 - **Sustainability of the overarching biodata resource infrastructure** - how can funders cooperate to develop and sustain the biodata resource infrastructure as a whole and ensure it meets the evolving needs of users?
33. This Section focuses on sustainability at the level of globally important biodata resources. Sustainability of the overarching infrastructure is addressed in Section 4. However, it should be emphasised that the premises and principles that are discussed in this section as a basis for models of cross-funder cooperation to support biodata resources also extend to cross-funder cooperation to sustain the infrastructure as whole.
34. As noted above, the Global Core Biodata Resources have been identified as a key initial focus for GBC efforts to develop cross-funder models to support sustainability. It is recognised that the initial list of GCBRs is not yet complete or fully globally representative. Further, it is important to recognise that many resources that do not meet the specific criteria for GCBR selection nevertheless play crucial roles in serving researchers in specific domains, and are also vitally important to fund and sustain.
35. However, the GCBR list does provide an initial set of resources whose long-term sustainability is vital to the global research community in the life sciences and biomedicine. There is therefore the potential for funders to work with the cohort of GCBRs to address the challenge of sustainability, and to identify and potentially trial new funding models and approaches to better support and sustain critical global resources of this type.

3.2 Draft premises and principles for cross-funder cooperation

36. The Working Group discussed a wide range of factors that would need to underpin successful cross-funder collaboration. These are organised below as draft premises and principles. This is a complex issue and the premises are intended as observations on, or assumptions relating to, the global infrastructure landscape; the Principles build on these Premises, and offer possible positions that GBC might adopt when developing models for global cooperation amongst funders and biodata resource managers that drive towards sustainability.

3.2.1 Premises

Premise 1: Biodata resources are essential tools for life science research globally - individually and collectively

37. Life science research, whether experimental or observational, wet-lab or computational, necessarily involves data. These data include those that are generated de novo in order to address a research question and those that pre-exist a given study and are used for comparison or reference purposes. The research process involves the management of data, including the submission of newly generated data, the publication of derived and/or curated data sets and use of pre-existing data sets. In all of these processes, biodata resources are essential and universal tools to researchers. They have value to science and society both individually and also collectively - with the benefits of individual resources being amplified across the connected biodata resource infrastructure as a whole.

Premise 2: Coordinating biodata resource sustainability will bring efficiencies

38. Since nearly all researchers make use of biodata resources and all funding organisations are already supporting researchers who access and use biodata resources through their grants. Broader and more coordinated global support for sustaining biodata resources will allow improvement to user-facing interfaces and services, and strategic investment in advancing technical infrastructure, that are not currently possible on short-term grant funding. Greater global coordination will lower the burden of access and reduce in-project data management costs for researchers. Some opportunities for savings as a result of better coordination may also come in the form of identification and removal of unnecessary redundancy between biodata resources.

Premise 3: It will be necessary to define which biodata resources are included within global efforts to ensure long term sustainability

39. As noted above, GBC is working to help funders identify biodata resources that are most widely used in life science research globally, and which are priorities for sustainability at a global level. This work includes the Global Core Biodata Resource selection process and the Global Inventory project as described above. Together they will provide a mapping of the biodata resource landscape that will facilitate discussions about funding aspirations. Future work will include the identification and/or development of biodata resource life cycle management approaches that will ensure that data resources retain relevance or, where appropriate, deploy safe deprecation mechanisms.
40. It is recognised fully that individual funders will determine their own priorities, and have distinct areas of responsibility and focus. In addition to contributing to the sustainability of relevant biodata resources which fulfil the GCBR criteria, funders are entirely at liberty to prioritise support for data resources which may not fulfil the GCBR definition yet are of strategic importance to their communities.

Premise 4: Sustainability in biodata resources centres upon sustainable funding

41. The sustained operation of a biodata resource reflects many factors that go beyond funding. These include an active user community that maintains the flow of data into the data resource and helps to steer the resource's services; the running of programmes by data resource managers to link data with records in external databases in order to add context,

value and usability; and the operation of resource and content life cycle management that tracks technical and societal needs in order to keep data resources relevant, current and useful. All of these elements require that there is—at the centre—a viable, stable and sustained biodata resource around which activities can coalesce, and in which the users can have confidence.

Premise 5: Solving the sustainability problem will require new and innovative approaches

42. Addressing the complex challenges around sustainability should be seen as an opportunity to adopt creative approaches, with the prospect of increased global collaboration and benefits to research being the return on investment into finding a solution. In order to achieve sustainability, extensive change is required by many actors: funding organisations must adapt their programmes; biodata resource managers must be open to new models for funding provision, implementation and shared operation; and the wider scientific community must increase its awareness of, and place greater value upon biodata resources. These transitions will be difficult, but the end point will add value to life science for the benefit of all. GBC is mandated to support the transition across the actors, including supporting funding organisations in adopting new approaches, and working between the funding agencies and the biodata resource managers to align the necessary changes as they unfold.

3.2.2 Principles

Principle 1: Those who fund life science research share responsibility for ensuring that data resources are sustained

43. Just as biodata resources are essential tools for life science research, the sustainability of those resources is essential to life science research and should be of concern to all research funders and the international research community more broadly. GBC proposes that it is a responsibility of all research funding organisations to support, in significant, tangible and persistent ways, the sustainability of biodata resources - whether through funding this infrastructure directly or through working with other bodies at national and international levels. Because this infrastructure is a global good, it should also be of concern to international, cross-governmental organisations and there may be scope for them to also contribute.

Principle 2: Life science research funders of all types should contribute to biodata resource sustainability

44. If the costs of sustainability are shared across all life science research funders, the total burden on each funder will be manageable. Whilst the overall cost of developing, operating and sustaining the world's biodata resources is unknown, we estimate that it is at or below 1% of global life science research budgets. If broadly shared, the cost of sustainability relative to other aspects of research funding will remain very low.
45. The definition of “research funder” should be broad; while GBC membership is currently drawn from government-linked national and international research funding bodies and from the larger research foundations, organisations that fund life science research also include philanthropies, commercial entities, citizen advocacy groups, universities, and more. Since all of these groups support life science research, taking responsibility for research projects necessarily includes support—in some way—for sustainability in biodata resources. GBC must strive to develop support approaches appropriate for different types of research funders.

Principle 3: All life science research funders should contribute through means that are appropriate to their cases

46. Given that sustaining biodata resources is essential for life science research, all funders should contribute. However, there needs to be flexibility in how these contributions happen. For a major national funding organisation, a financial contribution would be expected. For some funders, constitutional barriers to funding (e.g., moving funds outside a specific scientific domain or beyond national borders), may necessitate the use of local or in-kind contributions, such as the hosting of components of a biodata resource, or the secondment of staff, rather than fund transfers. For low and middle-income countries, limited resources and prohibitive currency exchange rates may require the development of funding rate reduction, such as is practised by some scholarly publishers.

Principle 4: Sustainability will be required both for existing resources and for new resources that are established to respond to new data types and technologies

47. The rich ecosystem of existing biodata resources support biodata derived from different analytical platforms and for different scientific purposes. These existing data resources suffer from low sustainability and are an immediate target of concern for GBC. There are existing gaps in biodata resource provision with some data types and research fields not well served by existing biodata resources. New life science analytical platforms will also emerge over time yielding data and supporting science that requires the design and development of new biodata resources to operate alongside those that already exist.
48. Although establishing sustainability in a new biodata resource from the outset will likely be easier than adapting the funding arrangements for an existing resource, established biodata resources must also remain as targets for sustainability interventions despite the challenges. Furthermore, the models for sustainability must be appropriate for funding organisations' biodata resource life cycle management mechanisms that are in place to guide the development, maturation and sunsetting of biodata resources.

Principle 5: Models of funding must not require payment at the point of use of biodata resources (submission, retrieval, etc.)

49. The GBC's Letter of Understanding as signed by its member funders states that, "the GBC should take as a fundamental principle that life sciences and biomedical biodata resources should be open and freely available to all".
50. Models that involve the direct allocation of funds from research funding organisations to support biodata resources will offer the least "friction" for those using the resources, enable a simple basis for charging (such as the contribution of a given proportion of the funder's overall research budget) and allow for the greatest transparency (contributions will be more directly and readily measurable).
51. In contrast, indirect mechanisms — such as charging researchers at the point of use for data services (such as deposition and retrieval) with subsequent reimbursement through grant agreements — would bring complexity and friction for funder and researcher alike and may discourage researchers from making full use of data resources (including sharing their data appropriately) if it requires them to allocate funds from research budgets. Whilst indirect

mechanisms may be simpler to adopt in the short term, GBC must seek sustainability models that are themselves sustainable even if such models require more effort or time to set up.

52. Whilst members of the Working Group believed strongly in the principle that resources should be free at the point of use, some qualifications and potential future challenges to this principle were noted. In particular:

- This principle may not always extend to managed access resources, which may often seek to recover the costs of managing access requests through standard charges to those accessing the data. Expecting resources and funders to commit to cover the costs of all requests for access may be problematic. In addition, and as noted further below, further conditions on access may be required to respect data sovereignty and ensure equitable benefit sharing in line with the CARE principles and other standards.
- The move to cloud-based computing is creating questions of how the associated costs should be provisioned, as the ability of users to access and analyse huge volumes of data grows. Whilst the costs for most research users will be modest, the cost for some high-volume users, for example those working with large-scale genomic or imaging datasets, might be considerable. Funders are increasingly concerned that they cannot commit to providing these costs for all users of a resource. This is an issue which, for example, the US National Institutes of Health is actively considering and addressing—including through the [STRIDES initiative](#).

Principle 6: Models for sustainability must cater for cases where funds cannot move across national borders:

53. Moving funds across national borders will be challenging for some funders. For many funders, including some current GBC Member and Observer organisations, there are legal or administrative restrictions on moving funds internationally. Sustainability models must therefore allow for cases where funders—especially those linked to governments—are required to exert restrictions on the destination of their funds and on where funded activities take place.

Principle 7: Biodata resources must develop governance structures that support the interests of funding organisations and the institutions that host biodata resources

54. Models for the sustainability of biodata resources must allow for international cooperation in the sharing of funding support and the distribution of activities between biodata resources. Governance structures for biodata resources will need to adapt so that they continue to function in the best interests of the biodata resources and their users. These mechanisms must allow multiple contributing institutions to support the delivery of a biodata resource, but must also reflect the needs of the user community around the resource. The long term successful operation of a data resource is a shared responsibility: the funders frame the policy, the data resource managers implement the operation and life cycle systems, and the community steers the services while both supplying and exploiting the data.

Principle 8: Sustainability across the biodata resource ecosystem depends upon the openness of data they hold

55. Open data is a value multiplier and is key to sustainability. With openness comes greater usage, which is itself required to attract feedback on data resource content, interfaces and services. This greater usage includes the capture of a data resource's content by

computational tools and secondary data resources that analyse, integrate and curate to add context and utility. Open data can be linked; allowing users to discover collections of relevant data sets and to integrate cross-domain data sets to support their research questions.

56. Without open data, the power of modern high-throughput analytical platforms will not be realised: any one run of a sequencing machine, for example, yields more data than needed to answer the scientific question at hand. These data sets have a rich information content that can emerge over time if they are exposed to the broadest scientific user communities.
57. The Working Group acknowledged fully that not all data can be fully open and unrestricted, and that controls and limits on access are essential where data relate to human subjects or present other risks - for example, to biodiversity or biosecurity. In addition, where data are collected from indigenous groups and other communities, data must be accessed and used in a way that respects sovereignty and equitable benefit sharing. The need to embed global equity in the implementation of open data policies, and reflect emerging good practice standards, including the CARE Principles, is highlighted in the consultation paper developed by the GBC Working Group on Open Data Strategies.
58. For managed access resources, this principle would extend to ensuring that data and metadata are as open as possible, whilst ensuring proportionate controls and safeguards are in place to manage risks.

Principle 9: All biodata resources should have a clear strategy for sustainability, including appropriate succession plans

59. Ongoing support for an essential biodata resource requires a major commitment from its funding organisation(s). While the commitment to support a biodata resource may be made with the greatest intent at one time, the possibility of political pressure, in the event of major strategic change in policy direction, will always bring risks that support will be terminated or reduced. For this reason, it is important resources work with funders to establish long-term plans for sustainability and succession plans, and work to diversify funding where this helps mitigate any risks associated with reliance on single funders.

3.3 Illustrative models for cross-funder cooperation

60. In order to illustrate how these principles might be operationalised, the Working Group discussed a series of initial models for how cooperative arrangements could work in practice. As is discussed in Section 4 below, the Working Group emphasised that raising the overall level of funding for biodata resources was a critical priority in its own right that should be pursued alongside consideration of cooperative funding models.
61. In discussing potential models for coordination, the Working group also emphasised that:
 - **There will not be a one-sized fits all solution** — different approaches will work for different resources and different funders. It will be important to develop and test different models and assess the circumstances under which they might add value.
 - **It is vital to build on what is working well** — whilst there is a need to engage new funders and develop more sustainable models for many resources, some resources have models in place which have worked well to date both from the perspective of the resource and their funders. Group members emphasised the need to learn from and build on these models where they exist and not to replace these mechanisms unnecessarily.

62. The initial models that were considered by the Working Group are illustrated in **Annex B**. These models are simplified and are intended as a starting point for cross-funder dialogue, and consultation with biodata resources and the broader community. Based on these discussions, it will be possible to develop more comprehensive models. The models are not mutually exclusive: elements of different models could potentially be combined.
63. The initial models are based around GCBRs being operated through distributed funding sources, distributed personnel and distributed infrastructure:
- **Model 1 (distributed funding sources support a biodata resource)**—international funders contribute to a common fund (in proportion to total research spend), which is then allocated between an agreed set of biodata resources via a centralised mechanism. A variation on this model would be that contributions from funders are made proportionally to levels of usage by their funded researchers of the biodata resources that are included.
 - **Model 2 (a biodata resource is operated by distributed personnel)**—funders pay for activities in institutions and staff at those institutions then contribute to resources globally in line with need, through for example secondments or dedicating part of their time to supporting resources based elsewhere.
 - **Model 3 (components that make up a biodata resource are distributed)**—funders support institutions which contribute specific components, activities or functions of resources. Under this model many resources would be highly distributed with sub-components at a variety of institutions around the world.
 - **Model 4 (biodata resources are operated from multiple locations)**—funders contribute to resources in-country which serve researchers at a national level but are part of larger coordinated resources at global level. A variation on this model would involve coordination at regional level (adopting a comparable approach to ELIXIR and H3ABioNET)
64. It is notable that elements of these models are in place, or have been in place, for some of the GCBRs. Exploration of experiences of GCBR managers will provide important insight as the models are investigated, developed further and tested.
65. These models are based on the assumption that funders will need and are willing to take on the mantle of supporting long-term funding and sustainability for resources, so that they can continue to serve the research community and provide access free at the point of use. As noted above, models that require restricting access via a paywall to some or all parts of the dataset were not considered to be in line with GBC’s values and aims.
66. Two other potential funding models were raised in discussions — although these may not be viable in all circumstances, it was felt they should be factored into further discussions:
- **Mixed ‘commercial’ models**—in some circumstances, it may be feasible for resources to generate revenue whilst still providing free and open access to the data they hold. This can include the use of ‘freemium’ models, where access to the data is free for all, but additional value-added services and tools are offered in return for a fee. There may also be potential for some widely used resources to generate advertising revenue. It was noted that, where attempted, such approaches have often failed to generate sufficient revenue for the resources concerned to impact significantly on its long-term dependence on funders (see Gabella et al 2018). Nevertheless, these may be viable and useful additional options for some resources in some circumstances.

- **‘Tax-based’ models**—models have been proposed in other areas (for example, development of medicines for diseases where effective markets do not exist) where funds for areas of unmet need are generated through a micro-levy on an unrelated transaction (for example, purchase of a ticket for air travel). For biodata resources, the most likely application of such a model would be some form of ‘tax’ on research grants (e.g. a very small percentage of each grant awarded flows into a central mechanism to support essential infrastructures). It would be extremely challenging to bring together and coordinate public, charitable and commercial funders globally to implement parallel solutions, but this might change in the future.

3.4 Options proposed

67. The Working Group is keen to invite comments and feedback from funders, biodata resource managers and the broader research community on the draft premises, principles and models set out above as a basis for further collaborative work to develop and test models to enable cooperative approaches to fund and sustain biodata resources, with a focus on the most vital resources internationally. The options presented are summarised in **Box 2** overleaf.

Box 2 — Options for funders in sustaining biodata resources of global importance

- a. Establish the broad principles set out in the Consultation Paper as a foundation** to develop shared approaches for the support of crucial biodata resources of international importance. These principles are:
- Those who fund life science research share responsibility for ensuring that data resources are sustained.
 - Life science research funders of all types should contribute to biodata resource sustainability.
 - All life science research funders should contribute through means that are appropriate to their cases.
 - Sustainability will be required both for existing resources and for new resources that are established to respond to new data types and technologies.
 - Models of funding must not require payment at the point of use of biodata resources (submission, retrieval, etc.).
 - Models for sustainability must cater for cases where funds cannot move across national borders.
 - Biodata resources must develop governance structures that support the interests of funding organisations and the institutions that host biodata resources.
 - Sustainability across the biodata resource ecosystem depends upon the openness of data they hold
 - All biodata resources should have a clear strategy for sustainability, including appropriate succession plans.
- b. Document current funding and sustainability plans for GBC Global Core Biodata Resources:** identify models that have worked well and use these to refine and add to the initial models presented in this Consultation Paper. This work will be conducted in partnership with GCBR Forum, and with partner funders to ensure that the models identified are viable and meet the needs of funders and resources.
- c. Prototype and test potential models to enhance sustainability in partnership with GCBR resources and GBC funders:** develop pilots of models supported by resources and funders to test their viability and success in enhancing sustainability.

4. Developing and sustaining the global biodata resource infrastructure

4.1 Issues considered by the Working Group

68. In addition to cooperating to support biodata resources, it is important that funders coordinate their efforts to ensure the overarching infrastructure, which is comprised of these resources, is developed and sustained in an effective manner that maximises the connections between resources, embeds standards and good practices, and anticipates technological developments and the evolving needs of user communities.
69. First and foremost, the Working Group emphasised that raising overall levels of funding for biodata resource infrastructure and raising the overall numbers of funders who commit to supporting biodata resources was critical to sustainability and should be pursued by GBC as an urgent priority, alongside the development of cooperative funding approaches (as described in Section 3). It was felt that even if new funders only commit to support selected resources in a national or regional context, this is still a valuable step.
70. To this end, It was suggested that the GBC could consider coordinating a campaign to engage funders around the sustainability issue. Such a campaign could include a specific declaration or pledge made by the funders, such as to declare commitment to the goals of GBC or to allocate a minimum percentage of total life science research spend to support and sustain data infrastructure over time. As estimates indicate this would require one percent of total research spend - this might be an appropriate level for such a pledge. However, it was noted that the feasibility and potential risks would need to be carefully thought through. Whatever form such a campaign takes, it was suggested that it should emphasise current and emerging evidence on the return on investment from funding biodata resources and the critical role of biodata resources in implementing FAIR and open data policy mandates.
71. In order to underpin campaign and advocacy efforts, it was felt to be vital to continue to build this evidence base on the value of biodata resources. GBC is ideally placed to bring together funders and resources to progress this, and the GCBR Forum could play a key role in developing approaches to measure usage and impact across resources, identify compelling case studies from across the GCBRs and target these to the needs of different funders.
72. In addition to increasing and stabilising funding, the long-term sustainability of the overarching infrastructure has several key aspects. Some of the key elements include:
- **Coverage** - including gaps in current provision across scientific domains and data types and emerging needs;
 - **Responsiveness** - ensuring the infrastructure evolves to meet emerging technological needs and anticipates the needs of research and user communities;
 - **Service standards** - services are stable, and embed appropriate technical and good practice standards to serve the needs of funders and researchers.
 - **Connectivity** - appropriate interconnectivities are developed and maintained both between resources within the infrastructure and between biodata resources in neighbouring fields and domains.
 - **Capacity** - the infrastructure has the technical and resource capacity to manage data volumes and usage requirements

- **Inclusiveness** - the infrastructure is globally inclusive and any barriers to participation are minimised
- **Efficiency** - the infrastructure operates in a manner that seeks to maximise efficiencies, economies of scale and cost effectiveness

73. The Working Group felt the GBC could play a key role in bringing together funders and resources to explore how they could cooperate most effectively to anticipate and address these aspects of sustainability, and to identify and discuss emerging trends and needs. GBC could also play an important role in identifying good practice principles for managing biodata resources across the resource lifecycle, including arrangements for establishing, sustaining and sunseting resources at the appropriate time.

4.2 Options proposed

74. In summary, the Working Group emphasised the need for funders to consider the development and sustainability of the infrastructure as a whole to ensure it evolves and grows to meet the needs of users. The options identified are set out in **Box 3** below.

Box 3 —Options for funders in advancing biodata resource sustainability globally

- a. **Secure enhanced and sustained funder investment in biodata research infrastructure** - including sustained long-term commitments from funders who already support biodata resources and encouraging funders who don't currently fund biodata resources to provide support in line with their remits. This might include:
 - i. developing a public campaign for funders to pledge their long-term commitment to supporting biodata infrastructure in a sustainable manner.
 - ii. working collectively to build the evidence base on the return from investment from providing sustained funding to biodata resources.
- b. **Coordinate approaches to ensure the stability and sustainability of the global biodata infrastructure** - GBC could play a key role in convening cross-funder efforts aimed at:
 - i. establishing good practice principles for funders on sustaining biodata resources throughout the resource lifecycle, including provisions for sunseting resources
 - ii. ensuring the biodata infrastructure develops to meet the evolving needs of research and user communities - tracking and responding to emerging trends and gaps in terms of domain coverage
 - iii. working with biodata resources to develop standards and good practices to ensure resources provide high quality, consistent, stable and responsive services for user communities.

Annexes

Annex A: Membership of the GBC Board Working Group on Sustainability

Name	Affiliation
Warwick Anderson (Chair)	Chair of GBC Board of Funders
Christophe Dessimoz	Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics (representing the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation, SERI)
Steve Ellis	US National Science Foundation (NSF)
Susan Gregurick	US National Institutes of Health (NIH)
Christiane Hertz-Fowler	Wellcome
Prashant Mathur	National Centre for Disease Informatics and research, India
Rowan McKibben	UK Research & Innovation (UKRI)
Claire O'Donovan	EMBL-EBI
Valérie Thibaudeau	Inserm, France
Daryl Waggott	Genome Canada

GBC Secretariat

Guy Cochrane

Chuck Cook

Rachel Drysdale

David Carr

Annex B: Illustrative Models for Cross-Funder Cooperation

1. Model 1 - Distributed funding sources support biodata resources

2. Model 2 - Biodata resources are operated by distributed personnel

3. Model 3 - Components that make up biodata resources are distributed

4. Model 4 - Biodata Resources are operated from multiple locations

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